

Research Article

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An assessment of the socio-economic factors that influence substance abuse among youths in the Gambia

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Abstract: The study's main aim was to assess socio-economic factors' influence on substance abuse among youths in The Gambia, for which a mixed-method approach was used, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis methods to understand the research objectives comprehensively. The study covered all regions of The Gambia using a Snowball Sampling method for the exercise, in which a total of 1,338 respondents were interviewed, out of which 99% of them are current substance users. In contrast, 1% are no longer involved in substance use. Out of the total respondents, 2% were female, while 98% were Male. To identify

the independent predictors of substance use, binary logistics regression was run, and the result was statistically significant (Chi-square = 51.911, $p < 0.001$; McFadden R-square = 0.046; $N = 1,201$). Tertiary educational attainment significantly reduces the odds of using substance appropriately by 55.7% compared to the informal education ($B = -0.814$, $p = 0.014$), indicating that tertiary educational attainment is key preventive factors of substance use. Respondents who reported that their unemployment status has significantly higher odds of substance compared to those who believed it has no effect on their current use of substances ($B = 0.442$, $p = 0.009$). The descriptive statistics show that most of the respondents (50%) believe that their socio-economic status does not influence their use of substances and (64%) associate low-income status families with a higher likelihood of substance abuse among youths. Peer pressure, which many believe is greatly affecting young people nowadays, most of the participants (61%) believe that peer pressure significantly influenced the initial use of substances. The study recommends support programs like financial literacy workshops, youth development projects, and initiatives that create opportunities for youths, and vocational training should be implemented. This will mitigate the hardship of unemployment, reduce the loitering of many youths by engaging them in something, and help them know how to utilize the little resources they have.

Keywords – Low-income, Peer-influence, Socio-economic, Substance, Unemployment

1. INTRODUCTION

Substance abuse is one of the country's most alarming dangers that is grossly consuming the active youth of The Gambia, causing low participation in productive economic activities. Substance abuse can be understood as the consumption of harmful psychoactive substances, including alcohol and illicit drugs, that stimulate the human central nervous system to malfunction and, most of the time, lead to physical and moral destruction and active crime participation (World Health Organization, 2024; Olurishe, 2019). Substance abuse is the use of substances, the possession or distribution of which is unlawful under the Controlled Substances Act [21 U.S.C. 801 et seq.]. Meanwhile, the exact cause of drug usage is mostly not clear, but there are two commonly noticeable theories: either a genetic predisposition or a habit learned from others (Bava & Tapert, 2010), and its addiction has some hazardous repercussions of chronic devastating diseases (NIDA, 2024; Bava & Tapert, 2010; Patrick et al., 2012).

In the past decade, the abuse of illicit substances in The Gambia has surged dramatically. In the early 2000s, a small percentage of the youth were engaged with illegal substances. Recently, a considerable number of teenagers and youths have used illegal substances like "Kush," "Skong," tramadol, cocaine, ecstasy, marijuana, hallucinogens, and/or psychotherapeutic drugs for non-medical purposes. Statistics from Psychiatric Hospital show that 60% of their admission cases are on drug-induced psychosis, Drug Law Enforcement Agency of The Gambia (2017). A study by Bah (2018) examines the prevalence and determinants of drug abuse among commercial van casual apprentices in The Gambia, which highlights that peer pressure, family influence, availability and accessibility, poverty, and unemployment were the main drivers of substance abuse. It also shown that Tobacco, alcohol, and cannabis were the most prevalent substances among the survey population. This rise in substance abuse among young people has immensely contributed to higher rates of unemployment, leading to more theft and criminal activities related to the possession, buying, and selling of these illegal substances. Most people associate the prevalence of mental illness in The Gambia with the high rates of substance abuse among youths. The misuse of alcohol and other dangerous substances has increased in many countries, and the outlook is overwhelmingly worrying and this well-known detriment to individuals and all societies is what unites them, which has called for the need for cooperation between members of society to tackle drug abuse and its contributing factors. Over the past decade, the use of illicit substances in Africa in general and in Gambia in particular has rapidly increased. A study by Society Royal African (Society Royal Africa, 2020) highlighted that since 2000, Africa as a continent growth by 49%, also, and the number of years loss to disability due to mental and substance use has increased by 52%.

The issue of illegal drug usage necessitates urgent intervention due to its detrimental impacts on human population dynamics and social behavior. The socioeconomic determinants and suggested strategies to counteract illicit substance use among young people in The Gambia were analyzed in this study using a compartmental deterministic model for the dynamics of illicit substance misuse among the nation's youth population. By constructing suitable approaches, the global asymptotic stability of the illicit drug-free and illicit drug-present equilibria will help in establishing their control mechanisms. Sensitivity analysis was performed to gain insight into how the model parameters contribute to the dynamics of illicit substance usage.

Therefore, the University of The Gambia Students' Union, under its Education and Research Ministry, during the Students' Week 2024, took it as a moral responsibility as the highest learning institution to conduct a robust study on the influential determinants of substance abuse among youths in The Gambia. Understanding the factors that influence the use of illegal substances is significant in combating their rampant consumption and proffering sound and effective solutions to ensure the country's youth are saved from their harm.

2.1. Research questions

1. What are the socio-economic impacts of substance abuse on individuals and families in The Gambia?

2. How does the level of education impact the likelihood of substance abuse among Gambian youths?
3. What role does peer influence play in the initiation or continuation of substance abuse?
4. What is the availability and accessibility of rehabilitation services for substance abusers in The Gambia?

2.2. Research objectives

1. To identify the key socio-economic impacts of substance abuse on individuals and families in The Gambia.
2. To analyze the likelihood of Gambian youths' involvement in substance abuse, given their education level.
3. To assess the impact of peer influence on the initiation and continuation of substance abuse.
4. To assess the availability and accessibility of rehabilitation services for substance abusers in The Gambia.

2.3. Significance of the study

This research is significant as it provides a comprehensive understanding of the socio-economic factors contributing to substance abuse in The Gambia. The findings of this research are aimed at helping inform policymakers, healthcare providers, and community leaders in developing targeted interventions to reduce substance abuse and its associated harms. By addressing the socio-economic causes, the study aimed to contribute to the creation of a healthier and more reasonable society.

2.4. Scope of the study

This research aims to investigate the socio-economic factors that contribute to substance abuse among youths in The Gambia. The study is concentrated on comprehending how variables such as socio-economic variables like unemployment rate and income levels, levels of education, social and cultural norms such as peer influence, and awareness of accessibility of rehabilitation services influence substance abuse in The Gambia. Data was collected across all regions in The Gambia.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Over the recent years, the escalating issue of substance abuse among youth has cast a dark shadow over communities worldwide, in general, and The Gambia in particular. This troubling trend has led and is leading many of the young individuals to venture into varying illegal activities and encounter their daring consequences. This phenomenon has so many complications, such as negative health outcomes, involvement in risky behaviors, and educational commotion (Kyei-Gyamfi et al., 2024; Ebrima, Adams & Demant, 2024). Recently, literature has shown that socio-economic factors have strongly influenced illicit substance usage patterns (Marsiglia et al., 2024; Asante & Atorkey, 2023). To develop targeted interventions and prevention programs, it is important to understand how these factors influence substance use in the Gambian context.

2.5. Family socio-economic factors

Family environmental and socio-economic status are major contributing factors to the use of illicit substances among young individuals. A study by Foo et al. (2012) in rehabilitation centers in Malaysia highlighted that parental support and the family's economic status positively influence illicit substance misuse behaviors. Young individuals from lower-income families are more likely to be prone to illicit substance use due to the experience of often less supervision and higher exposure to stressors (Idowu & Aremu, 2023). Adolescents in Nigerian communities aged 12 to 19. The study demonstrated that young individuals from families with low income in Nigerian societies are prone to illicit substances due to psychological stress. A similar study by Kyei-Gyamfi et al. (2024) in adolescents in Ghana

aged 10 to 17 argued that households with stable structures and protective parental guidance strongly influence in reducing young individuals' illicit substance use.

2.6. Peer influence and social network

Peer influence, which is widely regarded as the main influential factor of the young individuals' use of illicit substances. Nega and Chacko (2021) carried a study on street children in Nekemte aged 12 to 18, Ethiopia. They found that young individuals in Nekemte are subjected to both positive and negative peer pressure, with peers assisting in both leadership responsibilities and behavioral guidance. A similar study by Bosi et al. (2022) in Nigeria. They argued that pressure significantly affect mental health outcomes in Nigeria. Kyei-Gyamfi et al. (2024) done a similar study in Ghana and concluded that Ghanaians a young individual with peers who use illicit substances were significantly more likely to use illicit substances. A multi country study by Kugbey et al. (2023) in Sub-Saharan African countries strengthen the argument that peer networks strongly influence illicit substance use in different Sub-Saharan African context.

2.7. Education and school engagement

Educational engagement, which is supposed to serve as protective centers against illicit substances use, many has turned to be a easy access and usage centers of illicit substances for many young individuals nowadays. A study by Ajayi and Somefun (2020) in Nigerians university students. They highlighted that Nigerian university students who were academically free were more to use illicit substances. Adolescents with lower educational attainments among men have higher probability of engaging in hazardous drinking and differentiated use patterns by gender, Campano et al. (2018). Similar studies in Sub-Saharan African countries in (2021, 2024) demonstrated that school connectedness, academic performance, and school attendance reduce the likelihood of illicit substance use. This shows vital of schools in providing both supervision and social capital to mitigate risks.

2.8. Life skills and preventive interventions

Life skills and prevention interventions serve as the fundamental pillars of preventing and fighting against adolescents' involvement of illicit substances use. Buhler, Schroder, and Silbereisen (2008) carried a study in German among the fifty-grade students, and they demonstrated that life skills promotion positively influenced nicotine and alcohol use the fifth-grade students. A similar study by Brunn et al. (2021) in Nigeria's young adult in nightlife setting highlighted the effectiveness and efficiency environmental, structural, and microlevel interventions directed to young adult nightlife behaviors. A systematic review by (Uganda Ministry of Health, 2024; Demant, Adams, & Ebrahim, 2024) in Uganda and Sub-Saharan African countries respectively further reinforce this argument that life skills promotion, such as community engagement, family support, and life skills promotion are the most efficient and effective in discouraging young individuals from involving into illicit substances use. These insights highlighted the importance of life skills, family support, and community engagement helping young individuals avoid or reduce using illicit substances.

2.9. Community control

A community or society where young individuals live plays a crucial role in their involvement of illicit substance use. This is because a community where parents strictly supervised their children and where most children acquired economical skills, there is less likely for someone to be involved in substance use. A study by the Uganda's ministry of health in Kampala justified the claimed. They highlighted that young individuals who live in high density and

low resource community are more likely to expose to illicit substances use, as a result the limited parental supervision, community norms, and peer pressure (Uganda Ministry of Health, 2024). A similar study in Sub-Saharan African countries by Kugbey et al., (2023) further reinforce the claimed that urban residence and community deprivation are key influential risk factors of substance use in adolescents. These findings highlighted the importance of community collaboration in fighting and preventing illicit substances use in the community.

2.10. Employment status, age, and gender

Employment status, which is argued as one of the most influential factors of substance use and some socio-demographic factors like age and gender interact with socio-economic factors that influence substance use. A study by Teixido-Compano et al. (20218) in Spain highlighted that men with lower educational levels were more likely to use hazardous alcohol and cannabis and women are more likely to use hypnotics. Young adult that are engaged in nightlife environment and are more likely to accept and use illicit substances, Brun, Brunner and Mutsch (2021), a cross-sectional study in Switzerland. Adolescents' men are generally at a higher likelihood of risk for substance use, amplify by deprivation and employment status, Sub-Saharan African studies by (Asante & Atorkey, 2023; Kugbey et al., 2023).

Researchers like Nega and Chacko (2021) conducted a study on the "Effect of Peer Pressure on Youth Drug Abuse" in NEKEMTE, which is in Western Ethiopia. They concentrated on young individuals, and the participants in the study were 18 years old. Data was acquired from 12 street children and a few employees. According to the findings, peers perform a leading and protective function, as well as giving and encouraging influence and leadership responsibilities. Street youths are subject to both negative and positive peer pressure.

Foo et al. (2012) examine the impact of "Family Factors and Peer Influence in Drug Abuse" in rehabilitation clinics. This study discovered that familial characteristics (such as family economic standing) and peer influence were essential in determining an individual's drug misuse behaviors. It was also discovered that factors such as curiosity, stress relief, and betrayal by a spouse contributed to the participant's drug misuse. The study also discovered that drug abuse is frequently the result of a combination of numerous causes rather than a single factor.

Bosi et al. (2022) looked into the effect of "Peer pressure and substance use as predictors of mental health among in-school adolescents in Nigeria." This study used a cross-sectional research methodology, with a sample size of 288 in-school adolescents aged 13 to 22. According to the study's findings, peer pressure and substance abuse are detrimental to mental health.

Loke & Mak (2013) studied the effects of "Family Pressure and Peer Influences on Substance Use by Adolescents" in Hong Kong, China. A total of 805 pupils were chosen from secondary schools. The study found that teenagers with authoritarian parents were more prone to smoke. Adolescents who dispute with their parents are more likely to drink. People who have lenient parents are less prone to drink. Adolescent smoking and drinking were primarily caused by having friends who smoked or drank, as well as invitations from friends to smoke or drink.

Teixidó-Companó et al. (2018) analyzed the "Differences between men and women in substance use: the role of educational level and employment status" within Spain. A cross-sectional study was conducted using data from the 2013 Spanish Household Survey on Alcohol and Drugs on people aged 25 to 64. The association between the dependent and independent variables was examined using a Poisson regression model with robust variance. According to the study, men were more likely to engage in hazardous drinking and extensive cannabis use, whereas women used more hypnotics. It was also discovered that the lower the educational level, the higher the gender disparity in the prevalence of these substances due to distinct consumption patterns in men and women. Men with a lower educational level were more likely to drink hazardously and use cannabis heavily.

Brunn et al. (2021) conducted a study on "Interventions for Young Adults in Nightlife". In this study, young individuals aged 18 to 35 were included. They utilized microlevel, environmental, and structural approaches in Switzerland to carry out their study. The result shows that blood alcohol concentration calculation led to a significant increase in drinking frequency compared to controls in a Swedish study among university students with established levels of risky drinking.

Adebiyi (2008) carried out a similar study in Nigeria; they assessed the relationships as determinants of substance use amongst street children in a local government area in southwest Nigeria. From November 2004 to March 2005, a cross-sectional analytical study of street children was done in a local government region in southwestern Nigeria. A group-based sampling strategy was employed to enroll 360 consenting street children in the study. The data found that fifty-three percent of the respondents were current psychoactive substance users, with the five most prevalent substances used being kola nuts (58.6%), alcohol (43.6%), tobacco (41.4%), marijuana (25.4%), and "sokudaye" (24.9%). Respondents who live alone and whose fathers work outside the town were more likely to identify as current users (84% and 57.9%, respectively, $P < 0.05$).

Buhler et al. (2007) investigated "The role of life skills promotion in substance abuse prevention: a mediation analysis." In this study, they used a sample of 442 fifth-grade students who took part in a quasi-experimental preventative study. The findings indicate that an improved understanding of life skills is accompanied by an increase in students' distant attitudes regarding alcohol and nicotine usage.

Bah (2018) investigated the risk and prevalence of drug misuse among street children in The Gambia, with a focus on those in car parks. He focuses primarily on six critical areas: level of knowledge of drug abuse, perception of it, level of knowledge of the causes of it in the community and among street children, level of knowledge of the negative consequences, level of knowledge of preventive methods, and level of knowledge of the support services and treatments required by victims; a structured questionnaire was used to collect data from thirty-five participants. The findings revealed that there is a prominent level of awareness about drug misuse, yet opinions about it are conflicting. Street children, like other children, use drugs primarily because of peer pressure, with the main purpose of getting high to relieve stress, gain group recognition, and be trusted by peers.

Olurische and Bello (2019) carried out an extensive review of "Drug and Substance Abuse in Anglophone West Africa" and found that in The Gambia, there is less current information on drug use and patterns than in Nigeria. In Liberia, a survey of 802 children in 16 secondary schools found no significant difference in overall drug use based on age or gender, and the majority of respondents (78%) had previously used alcohol.

Embleton et al. (2014) utilized meta-analytical methodologies to synthesize literature that matched the review's inclusion criteria, and pooled prevalence estimates were derived using the random-effects model for lifetime substance use by geographical location and substance type. The study concluded that street adolescents from resource-constrained households had a high lifetime of substance usage. The most commonly used substances are inhalants, followed by tobacco, alcohol, and marijuana.

Chie et al. (2015) did a review on "Drug abuse, relapse, and prevention education in Malaysia" to examine university students' perspectives on this phenomenon. They collected data via questionnaires, using 460 university students from five Malaysian states as participants. The findings revealed gender variations in perceptions of relapse prevention measures, as well as factors that contribute to drug abuse and relapse. It also showed that students believed that drug education would be more effective if it began between the ages of 11 and 12 years, which is slightly older than the average age of first exposure.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Substance misuse among youths is becoming an increasing concern in The Gambia, posing considerable risks to both individual and social well-being. Despite many interventions, the rate of substance misuse keeps rising, particularly among young people. This trend is influenced by many socioeconomic factors: elevated levels of unemployment, poverty, a lack of educational possibilities, and societal instability. However, this literature explored thorough research on these characteristics and their proportional impact on youth substance misuse in The Gambia. Understanding the socioeconomic variables is essential for establishing effective preventative and intervention plans for policymakers, educators, and healthcare providers to address this pressing issue more effectively.

4. METHODOLOGY

A mixed-methods approach was used, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis methods for this study. Due to limited information on the socio-economic factors that influence substance abuse among youths in The Gambia, a mixed method provides comprehensively understanding about phenomena, particularly in complex ones that neither method alone can offer (Ostlund, Kidd, Wengstrom, & Dewar, 2010). The use of mixed research method also enables to tackle broad and complex research questions (Smajic, Avdic, Pasic, Prcic, & Stancic, 2022). Thus, the study adopted an exploratory research design using a micro survey (questionnaires, KIIs, and focus group discussions).

4.1. Types and sources of data collection

The quantitative part of the research was conducted using cross-sectional data. A structured questionnaire was administered to gather quantitative data on socioeconomic factors, education level, peer pressure, and substance abuse. We deployed fifty (50) enumerators to do the data collection processes for both the qualitative and quantitative data in all regions of the country (LRR, CRR, URR, NBR, WCR, and GBA). The qualitative data were based on focus group discussions and key informant interviews with stakeholders; this helped to see the conceptual view of community leaders and relevant stakeholders on the study. Survey Solution software was used as a quantitative data collection tool. The data was stored on the Survey Solution demo server and retrieved in the format (.dta and .csv). Due to the difficulty in accessing the total number of substance users, we explored a snowball sampling method for the exercise. A total of 1,338 respondents were interviewed, out of which 99% are still using substances, while 1% are no longer users.

In the qualitative data collection, semi-structured interviews with key informants, including healthcare providers (MoH), DLEAG, educators, social workers, and community leaders, were conducted. In the same vein, focus group discussions with youth and community group leaders were conducted across all LGAs in rural areas to gather in-depth insights into their experiences and perceptions of substance abuse. For the KII, the team visited the Ministry of Health and DLEAG to conduct the key informant interviews.

4.2. Study area

The first phase of the study was conducted in the Lower River Region (LRR), with subsequent phases extending to other areas in The Gambia; this included the Central River Region (CRR), North Bank Region (NBR), West Coast Region (WCR), and Greater Banjul Area (GBA). Overall, the study covered at least three (3) districts in each region.

4.3. Data analysis

Simple descriptive statistics were explored using the latest version of STATA Statistical Software (STATA 18). This included central tendency measures (mean, median, mode), standard deviation, and graphical representations. For the qualitative part, following the completion of the data collection, audio recordings were transcribed and analyzed using content and thematic analysis for the FGD and KII. The analysis focused on identifying key themes and insights relevant to the research objectives.

4.4. Ethical consideration and quality assurance

Study participants received full information on the purpose, confidentiality, and their rights to quit participation. Participation was voluntary, and participants could withdraw at any time without consequence. Enumerators and supervisors were trained on data collection, ethics, and the use of tools to ensure accuracy. This tool was pilot-tested in a small sample of HCPs for streamlining and refinement before being fully implemented. Coordinators monitored adherence to protocols and quality through ongoing supervision.

5. DATA PRESENTATION AND FINDINGS

Table 1: Demography

Demographic	Count	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Female	1338.00	0.02	0.13	0.00	1.00
Male	1338.00	0.98	0.13	0.00	1.00
Relationship with the guardian	Count	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Father	1338.00	0.49	0.50	0.00	1.00
Mother	1338.00	0.24	0.43	0.00	1.00
Uncle/Aunt	1338.00	0.06	0.24	0.00	1.00
Grandparents	1338.00	0.05	0.22	0.00	1.00
Sibling	1338.00	0.05	0.21	0.00	1.00
Other	1338.00	0.10	0.30	0.00	1.00
Education Level of Respondent	Count	Mean	SD	Min	Max
ECD	1338.00	0.00	0.07	0.00	1.00
Primary	1338.00	0.19	0.39	0.00	1.00
Upper Basic	1338.00	0.26	0.44	0.00	1.00
Senior Secondary	1338.00	0.24	0.43	0.00	1.00
Tertiary	1338.00	0.06	0.23	0.00	1.00

Informal	1338.00	0.18	0.38	0.00	1.00
No education	1338.00	0.07	0.26	0.00	1.00
Education Type of Guardian	Count	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Formal	1338.00	0.35	0.48	0.00	1.00
Informal	1338.00	0.45	0.50	0.00	1.00
Apprenticeship	1338.00	0.08	0.28	0.00	1.00
None	1338.00	0.11	0.31	0.00	1.00
Education Level of Guardian	Count	Mean	SD	Min	Max
ECD	470.00	0.03	0.18	0.00	1.00
Primary	470.00	0.08	0.27	0.00	1.00
Upper Basic	470.00	0.13	0.34	0.00	1.00
Senior Secondary	470.00	0.40	0.49	0.00	1.00
Tertiary	470.00	0.36	0.48	0.00	1.00
Never been school	470.00	0.00	0.05	0.00	1.00
Age of Respondent	Count	Mean	SD	Min	Max
43040	1338.00	0.05	0.23	0.00	1.00
18-35	1338.00	0.70	0.46	0.00	1.00
36-40	1338.00	0.16	0.37	0.00	1.00
Above40	1338.00	0.09	0.28	0.00	1.00
Region	Count	Mean	SD	Min	Max
GBA	1338.00	0.24	0.43	0.00	1.00
WCR	1338.00	0.14	0.35	0.00	1.00
LRR	1338.00	0.09	0.29	0.00	1.00
NBR	1338.00	0.14	0.34	0.00	1.00
CRR	1338.00	0.21	0.41	0.00	1.00

URR	1338.00	0.18	0.39	0.00	1.00
Local Government Area	Count	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Banjul	1338.00	0.06	0.24	0.00	1.00
Kanifing	1338.00	0.18	0.38	0.00	1.00
Brikama	1338.00	0.14	0.35	0.00	1.00
Mansakonko	1338.00	0.09	0.29	0.00	1.00
Kerewan	1338.00	0.14	0.34	0.00	1.00
Janjanbureh	1338.00	0.12	0.32	0.00	1.00
Kuntaur	1338.00	0.09	0.29	0.00	1.00
Basse	1338.00	0.18	0.39	0.00	1.00
Annual Income of Household	Count	Mean	SD	Min	Max
Less than D50,000	1338.00	0.39	0.49	0.00	1.00
D50,000- D100,000	1338.00	0.34	0.47	0.00	1.00
D100,000- D150,000	1338.00	0.16	0.37	0.00	1.00
D151,000- D300,000	1338.00	0.07	0.25	0.00	1.00
D300,000- D500,000	1338.00	0.02	0.14	0.00	1.00
Above D500,000	1338.00	0.01	0.09	0.00	1.00
Cannot say	1338.00	0.01	0.09	0.00	1.00

Overall, 1338 respondents were interviewed during the data collection process. Of the respondents, 2% were female, while 98% were male. The majority of respondents identified their father (49%) as their guardian, while 25% identified their mother as their guardian. The remaining percentage was shared among other guardians. Out of the total respondents interviewed, 24% were from the Greater Banjul Area (GBA), 14% were from the West Coast Region (WCR), 9% from the Lower River Region (LRR), 14% were from the North Bank Region (NBR), 21% from the Central River Region (CRR), and 18% from the Upper River Region (URR).

In the case of the education level of respondents, 24% reported that senior secondary was their highest level of education and 45% of respondents' guardians attended informal education. On the aspect of household income, 39% of the respondents interviewed recorded that their household income is less than fifty thousand Dalasi (D50, 000). Most of the respondents interviewed were within the age bracket of 18-35 (70%) and 36-40 (16%). This shows that the majority of the respondents were within the youth age range.

Table 2: The Relationship Between Respondent’s Educational Leve and Substance Use

Respondent's current substance use status	level of education of the respondent							
	ECD	Primary	Upper Basic	Senior Secondary	Tertiary	Informal	None	Total
Yes	6	249	345	320	76	238	94	1328
	100.00%	99.20%	99.14%	99.38%	100.00%	99.17%	98.95%	99.25
No	0	2	3	2	0	2	1	10
	0.00%	0.80%	0.86%	0.62%	0.00%	0.83%	1.05%	0.75%
Total	6	251	348	322	76	240	95	1338
	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Pearson Chi2(6) = 0.8999 Prob = 0.989

A Pearson Chi-square (X^2) test of independence was performed to examine whether less educated youths are more likely to abuse substances. The result indicated that $X^2 = 0.8999$, Prob = 0.989, suggesting that there is no statistically significant relationship between the respondent’s level of education and the substance used in this sample. This is justified by the slight difference (percentages) in the number of individuals whose highest educational level is ECD (100%), Primary (99.2%), Secondary (99.3%), and Tertiary level (100%). However, educational levels don’t influence substance use patterns in this sample.

Table 2: The Relationship Between Respondent’s Current Substance use Status and Their Main Guardian

Respondent's current substance use status	The main guardian of the respondent						
	Father	Mother	Uncle/Aunt	Grandparents	Siblings	Other	Total
Yes	660	324	85	69	59	131	1328
	99.70%	99.39%	100.00%	98.57%	95.16%	98.50%	99.25%
No	2	2	0	1	3	2	10
	0.30%	0.61%	0.00%	1.43%	4.84%	1.50%	0.75%
Total	662	326	85	70	62	133	1338
	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Pearson Chi2 = 17.94 Prob = 0.0030

A Chi-square (X^2) test of independence was performed to examine the likelihood of respondents using substances given their main guardian. The Pearson Chi-square test, $X^2 = 17.94$, Prob = 0.0030, shows a statistically significant association between the respondent’s main guardian and substance use. However, individuals whose main guardians are their uncle and Anty (100%) are more likely to use illicit substances followed by those with their father as their main guardian (99.7%), and mother (99.39%) in this sample. These differences were statistically significant. Therefore, the respondent’s main guardian statistically influences substance use patterns in this sample.

Table 3: Binary Logistic Regression – Model Fit Statistics

Statistic	Value	Interpretation
Number of observation (N)	1.201	Valid cases after listwise deletion
Mean Dependent Variable	0.838	83.8% of the analytical users are current users
SD Dependent Variable	0.369	

Model Chi-square	51.911	P<.001 – model is statistically significant
McFadden Pseudo R ²	0.046	Acceptable for large social survey data
AIC (Akaike Information Criterion)	1,062.097	Benchmark for model comparison
BIC (Bayesian Information Criterion)	1,179.188	Benchmark for model comparison

The binary regression, model fit statistics, shows that, overall, the model was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 51.911$, $p < 0.001$), which highlighted that, collectively, the set of the socio-economic predictors improved the model fit beyond baseline null model. Although McFadden highlighted that Pseudo R² in binary regression are not comparable to the R² in ordinary regression, the McFadden pseudo-R² of 0.0446 shows modest, since it falls between 0.02 and 0.04, which generally indicate acceptable fit. The mean dependent variable of 0.838 indicates that 83.8% of the 1,201 valid cases were currently substance users, which is consistent with the method used to identify the study population

The table below represents the full binary regression output, including Z-statistics, two tailed p-value, robust standard errors (S.E), and coefficient (Coef). The model was estimated to use the enter method, with all predictors entered simultaneously.

Table 4: Binary Logistic Regression Output

Variable/Category	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Age Group (Ref: 11-17)							
36-40	.002	.226	0.01	.995	-.441	.444	
Above 40	-.483	.261	-1.85	.064	-.994	.028	*
Education Level (Ref: Informal)							
Primary	-.196	.257	-0.76	.445	-.7	.308	
Upper Basic	.345	.252	1.37	.171	-.149	.839	
Senior Secondary	-.168	.25	-0.67	.502	-.657	.322	
Tertiary	-.814	.331	-2.46	.014	-1.462	-.166	**
Annual Family Income (Ref: <50 000)							
D100,000-D150,000	-.107	.338	-0.32	.753	-.77	.556	
D151,000-D300,000	.295	.713	0.41	.679	-1.103	1.693	

D300,000-D500,000	-.111	.828	-0.13	.894	-1.734	1.512	
Can't say	-.207	.175	-1.18	.237	-.551	.136	
Economic Status (Ref: No)							
Not sure	-.97	.389	-2.49	.013	-1.733	-.207	**
Low Income Family ~N	0	
Not sure	.085	.3	0.28	.778	-.503	.672	
Unemployment Influence on substance abuse (Ref: No effect)							
Greatly increases	.442	.168	2.63	.009	.112	.772	***
Decreases	-.371	.658	-0.56	.573	-1.661	.92	
Greatly decreases	-.511	1.018	-0.50	.616	-2.507	1.485	
Family substance use (Ref: No)							
Yes	.259	.172	1.51	.131	-.077	.596	
Peer Pressure Contribution (Ref: Not At all)							
Somehow	-.332	.305	-1.09	.276	-.93	.266	
Quite a bit	-.518	.253	-2.05	.041	-1.015	-.022	**
A great deal	-.423	.191	-2.22	.027	-.797	-.049	**
Guardian Education Type (Ref:informal)							
Apprenticeship	-.029	.308	-0.09	.926	-.632	.574	
None/Other	-.196	.27	-0.73	.466	-.725	.332	
Currently in status (Ref: Not in school)							
Current in school	-.507	.287	-1.77	.077	-1.069	.055	*
Constant	1.742	.265	6.56	0	1.222	2.263	***
Mean dependent var					0.838	SD dependent var	0.369
Pseudo r-squared	0.046	Number of obs			1201		
Chi-square	51.911	Prob > chi2			0.000		
Akaike crit. (AIC)	1062.097	Bayesian crit. (BIC)			1179.188		
*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$							

Participants who asserted that their unemployment status greatly influences their use of substances had significantly larger odds in contrast with those who believed their unemployment status has no influence on their use of substances ($B = 0.442$, $S.E = 0.168$, $Z = 2.63$, $P = 0.009$, $CI: 0.112 - 0.772$). This shows that after controlling all other variables, this belief is independently associated with higher probability of current substance use. This finding is in line with the theory of cognitive dissonance, which highlighted that, individual will construct a justification belief to limit psychological discomfort as they engage in a behaviour they recognise as harmful. This is further justified by the qualitative part of this study, where individuals constantly cited lack of youth engagement and unemployment as main drivers of substance use among youths in The Gambia. This finding is also aligned with the studies done by (Kugbey et al., 2023, Asante & Atorkey, 2023) in Ghana, Nigeria, and Ethiopia, documented unemployment as a contextual risk factor for the initiation and continuation of substance use among young people.

Those who reported their highest level of educational attainment as tertiary had significantly higher odds in contrast with those with informal ($B = -0.814$, $S.E = 0.331$, $Z = -2.46$, $p = 0.14$, $CI: -1.462$ to -0.166). After controlling the

other variables and exponentiating the coefficient, the coefficient output an odd ratio approximately 0.443, which shows that respondents with tertiary education attainment had 55.7% lower odd ratio relatively to the ones with informal educational attainment. This shows that tertiary education is one of the preventive factors against continued use of substance in this study. This preventor factor works in many ways: higher educational achievement is highly correlated with higher risk awareness, greater trade-off for substance use, greater future orientation, and enhance cognitive resources for resisting peer pressure. This finding is aligned with a study done by Teixido-Compano et al., (2018) in Spain, which document that lower educational attainments were significantly related with cannabis and hazardous alcohol use. It is also justified by a study done in Sub-Saharan African by Kugbey et al. (2023), which demonstrated that educational engagement reduces the likelihood of substance use across divers country context. In the context of The Gambia, this finding has direct implication for educational policies: implementation of policies that will support young individuals' completion of secondary and tertiary levels, and reduction of financial barriers for higher education, which will to measurable long-term impacts in substance use prevalence among youths in The Gambia.

Respondents who perceived that peer pressure "greatly" contributed to their use of substances had significantly lower log-odds of current substance use compared to those who believed that peer pressure had no influence on their use of substances ($B = -0.423$, $S.E. = 0.191$, $Z = -2.22$, $p = 0.027$, 95% CI: -0.797 to -0.49), and the odd ratio of the ~ 0.655 present a 34.5% reduction in the ratio of current use and this also has similar findings as the "Quit bit option". The alignment of the Quit bit and the great deal confirm a reliable and statistically meaningful pattern. The participants who acknowledged peer pressure influence on their use of substances, paradoxically, the less likely still active substance users. The coherent of the two peer pressure findings, indicated that peer pressure as an influential factor of one's own of use of substances is greatly related with cessation and this pattern has vital policy implication like the creation of awareness programs to increase awareness youths and substance abusers in The Gambia.

The respondent who reported their age as above 40 years old had lower log-odds of current substance use compared to the base age group (11- 17), approaching statistical significance ($B = -0.483$, $S.E. = 0.261$, $Z = -1.85$, $p = 0.064$, CI: -0.994 to 0.028). The odd ratio of approximately 0.617 highlighted that respondents who report their as above 40 had approximately 38.3% of lower odd ratio of still being substance user, given the fact that this did not reach conventional significance. This finding is consistent with curse perspectives on substance use, which argued that substance tends to decline as a individual become older due to the prevalence of higher social responsibilities, which is incompatible with continuing substance use (Patrick et al., 2012).

Respondents who reported were currently going to school or engaged in formal learning had lower log-odds of current substance use compared to the base group (not in school currently). The odd ratio of approximately 0.617 highlighted that respondents who report being currently going to school or engaged in formal education had approximately 39.8% of being a substance user, though this did not reach conventional significance and also was not statistically significant in the bivariate analysis ($\chi^2(1) = 0.6988$, $p = 0.403$). This finding supports the broader literature on school connectedness as a protective factor against substance use (Demant, Adams, & Ebrahim, 2024).

The remaining predictor variables: gender(male), age-group (18-35 and 36-40), educational levels (Upper basic and senior secondary), all family monthly income levels, low income family status, unemployment (except great deal and a Quit bit), all guardian educational types, family substance use status, and peer pressure (except little and somehow) did not reach statistical significance level in the multivariate binary logistic regression model ($p > 0.05$), which indicated that after controlling other variables in the model, they do not independently distinguish current substance use from non-users in the study. However, their loss of significance in the regression model may reflect multicollinearity, inadequate statistical power arising from the high prevalence of substance use in this sample, or

the genuine mediation of their effect through the significant predictors but not meaning these variable has no relationship with the outcome

5.1. Information on substance and education

Figure 1: Types of Substances Use by the Respondents

The graph above (figure 1) illustrates the types of substances reported being used by respondents. It indicates that most of the respondents, 34.28% and 21.41% reported using cigarette-related substances and pills respectively, while 16% reported consuming Alcohol. Kush and Cocaine were reported by 7.77% and 2.82% respectively. Other types of substances like “Skong”, Harsh, Prince, and Tramadol were also reported. The findings indicate cigarette-related substances to be the most used substance among participants and are followed by weed. Also, other newly introduced substances like Kush and “Skong” are commonly used among participants.

Regional Comparison:

Figure 2: Substances have you used by Region

The graph above illustrates the types of substances reported being used by respondents, segmented by regions in The Gambia. The most prevalent substance used by substance abusers was cigarette-related substances with 46%, 42%, 41%, 45%, and 35% of respondents in CRR, GBA, LRR, NBR, URR, and WCR, respectively.

The second most prevalent substance is marijuana, with 33%, 34%, 41%, 31%, 36% and 34% taking it in CRR, GBA, LRR, NBR, URR, and WCR, respectively. The other types of substance abused include alcohol which is more prevalent in the GBA (11%), pills which is more prevalent in WCR (13%) and GBA (11%), Kush usage is seen to be more rampant in NBR (7%) followed by WCR and GBA with both accounting to 4% of the region’s total respondents respectively.

The results show that most substance users make use of cigarettes and their related substances, and the use of marijuana is also very high across all regions. This shows that more efforts need to go into sensitizing the youths about the dangers of the substances they are taking.

Age of respondents when they started using substances

Figure 3: Age First Started using Substances

The graph above shows the age distribution of respondents when first started using substances. It shows that 45% of the respondents reported first started using substances between the ages of 15-19, 30% started under the age of 15, and 18% started within the age of 20-24. Only 7% admitted that they started taking substances at the age of 25 and above.

The early consumption of substances has recently skyrocketed among young individuals, which has received much attention. The result indicated that most of the substance users started using substances when they were incredibly young, which was before they met the legal maturity age. A moderate percentage of the participants admitted to starting using the substances when they were 20 years and above.

The graph above shows the age distribution of respondents when they first started using substances, categorized by various regions in The. In the Greater Banjul, West Coast Region, and Lower River Region, about 26.90%, 38.10%, and 27.73% respectively of the respondents reported started using substances before they reached 15 years of age whereas 46.84%, 44.97%, and 42.86% respectively reported started taking substances between 15-19 years of ages, and 19.30%, 13.76, and 23.53% respectively reported between 20-24 years of age.

In North Bank Region, Central River Region, and Upper River Region, about 26.37%, 30.151%, and 29.63% respectively of the respondents reported started using substances before they reach 15 years of age, while 47.80%, 39.43%, and 48.15% respectively reported started taking substances between 15-19 years of ages, and 17.58%, 21.86, and 14.81% respectively reported between 20-24 years of age.

The data underscores a unanimous agreement across all regions. Across all regions, most of the participants started using substances before they reached the legal maturity age (18 years), and this highlights the consumption of illicit substances among young individuals in The Gambia.

Table 5: The Relationship Between Respondents' Substance Use and Their Age

Respondent's current substance use status	Age of respondent				
	11-17	18-35	36-40	Above 40	Total
Yes	73	928	212	115	1328
	100.00%	99.25%	98.60%	100.00%	99.25%
No	0	7	3	0	10
	0.00%	0.75%	1.40%	0.00%	0.75%
Total	73	935	215	115	1338
	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Pearson Chi2 = 2.63 Prob = 0.4518

The table above illustrates an independent Chi-square test on the relationship between substance use status and age group among the participants. It examines whether substance use status is correlated with the respondent's age group. The result highlighted that $X^2 = 2.63$, Prob = 0.4518, suggesting that there is no statistically significant relationship between age group and substance use among the respondents. Although it seemed slightly more common for individuals aged 11-17 and above 40 (100%), followed by those aged 18-35 (99.25%). These differences were statistically insignificant. Therefore, the age group doesn't influence substance use patterns in this sample. Substances among young individuals in The Gambia.

Figure 4: Contribution of Peer Pressure to Initial Use of Substances:

The graph above shows the contribution of peer pressure on participants' initial usage of illicit substances. A quite significant percentage of the respondents (61%) reported that their initial use of illicit substances was a result of peer pressure, while 39% disregarded the claim. To gain acceptance or avoid being labeled differently, many young individuals have given into the habit of their friends, and this has become a big concern to many parents. Peer pressure, which has become a big concern to many, particularly parents, is substantially supported by the findings.

Figure 5: School status at the first time of using substances:

The graph above reports the school going status of the respondents when they first started taking substances. It shows that 49% of the respondents reported they started using substances while they were going to school and 51% admitted that they started using substances after they either left or graduated. The quality of education and the rules and regulations observed in schools play a pivotal role in shaping the pupil's life. Though there is a close gap, a very significant percentage of the respondents reported started using substances while they were going to school and this made many youths to left school early and made students less value their education.

Figure 6: Families and Relatives Who Use Illicit Substances:

The graph above shows the correlation between participants' family members' drug use and the participants' drug use. It highlights that 67% of them reported that they had some family members who use illicit substances, while 33% noted that none of their family members use illicit substances. Early exposure to illicit substances has a variety of negative consequences for children, which could include substance use. The findings show that individuals whose families are substance users are more likely to be using substances, which could be a result of early exposure to illicit substances. It should also be noted that a significant percentage of the respondents are illicit substance users whose families are zero substance users.

Table 6: Association Between Family Substance Use and Youth Substance Use Patterns

Family or relatives that use illegal substances	Respondent's current sub use status		
	yes	No	Total
Yes	897	4	901
	67.55%	40.00%	67.34
No	431	6	437
	32.45%	60.00%	32.66
Total	1326	10	1338
	100.00	100.00	100.00
Pearson Chi2 = 3.42 Prob = 0.0643			

The table above shows the Pearson Chi-square test between the relationship between family substance use and respondent substance use pattern. It examines association between those who have family members who use substances and the likelihood of the respondent's using substances. The result indicated that there is no significant statistical relationship at 5% level ($p = 3.42$) between the variables, suggesting that individuals who have family members or relatives who use illicit substances are not more likely to subsequently use illicit substances in this sample.

Figure 7: Early Age Exposure to Illicit Substances by Family Members or Relatives

The graph above illustrates how often the respondents were used to being sent to buy illicit substances when they were young either by their family members or relatives. It shows that nearly half of the respondents (40%) admitted that they were always sent to buy illicit substances when they were young, while 31% admitted that they were sometimes sent to buy illicit substances by either their family members or relatives. Of the respondents, 29% reported to be using substances, but they had never been sent to buy illicit substances when they were young.

In Africa in general and Gambia in particular, it is a common cultural norm that children are usually sent on errands by elders, which is deeply rooted in obedience and values of respect, and this has exposed many children to illicit substances at early. The findings underscores that the young individuals who were exposed to illicit substances due to the common cultural norm has led many young individuals to adopt the habit of substance use.

Figure 8: Substance Taste Due to Child Curiosity While on Errands

The graph above illustrates the respondents who were usually sent to buy illicit substances when they were younger and subsequently tried it while they were on the errands. It shows that 54% show that they had tried illicit substances while they were being sent to buy them and 46% report that they had never given it a try when they were sent to buy these substances when they were young. This indicates that many of the substance users were exposed to illicit substances at an early age and, because of being sent to buy such substances, most of them had their first experience of it at an incredibly early age.

Table 7: The correlation Btw the Taste of Substances Due to Child Curiosity While on Errands and Substance Use

Taste substances out of curiosity as a child	Substance Use		
	yes	No	Total
Yes	580	4	584
	54.21%	44.44%	54.12%
No	490	5	495
	45.79%	55.56%	45.88%
Total	1070	9	1079
	100.00	100.00	100.00

Pearson Chi2 = 0.34 Prob = 0.5584

The table above shows the Pearson Chi-square test on the perception of respondents on the taste of substances due to child curiosity while on errands and substance use patterns. It examines whether young individuals who tasted substances at a very early age while on errands are more likely to subsequently use substances at 5% significant level. The result shows that there is no statistically significant relationship between the two variables, suggesting that children who tasted substances at an early age while on errands are not more likely to subsequently use substances in the sample.

5.2. Socio-economic factors

Figure 9: The Main Reason Youths in The Gambia Use Substances

The graph above shows the main reasons reported by respondents which have led them to give into the habit of substance use. Family-related problems are the most common factor cited by the respondents, with 62% acknowledging it as a reason, and it's followed by lack of employment opportunities, which is cited by 57% of the respondents. Peer pressure, economic stress, and curiosity are also major factors, with 55%, 36%, and 41% respectively acknowledging them as a reason for using substances. Other reasons like pleasure, poor parental care, and personal problems were also cited by the respondents as a reason for their involvement in substance use.

Figure 10: Perception of substance abuse prevalence among low-income families

The graph above illustrates respondents' perceptions about the prevalence of illicit substances among individuals from low-income families. The graph above illustrates respondents' perceptions about the prevalence of illicit substances among individuals from low-income families. It shows that a significant majority, 63%, of the respondents reported that substance abuse is common among individuals from low-income families, while 28% think it is not. Meanwhile, 9% do not have an opinion on the matter. This suggests that most people associate low-income status with a higher likelihood of substance abuse among youths, although a notable portion disagreed

Figure 11: Effect of unemployment on substance usage among youths in the Gambia

The graph above shows the perceived influence of unemployment on substance usage among youths in The Gambia. Of this, 85% of the participants indicated that the high rate of unemployment among the youths positively influenced the high rate of substance abuse in The Gambia. Meanwhile, 15% believe that unemployment has no effect on substance usage among youths while 1% believe that unemployment decreases substance abuse.

The result shows that unemployment on a greater scale influences the involvement of youths on substance abuse, with the majority of the participants believing that unemployment has greatly influenced the high rate of substance abuse among youths in The Gambia.

Figure 12: Regional Comparison

The Figure 12 above shows the perceptions of people on the influence of economic status on substance abuse among youths in The Gambia, categorized by region. In Central River Region, 51% of the participants reported that their use of substances is influenced by their economic status, while 46% claiming that their use of substances is not influenced by their economic status, and 3% are not sure.

The Greater Banjul and Lower River Region show that 49% and 48% respectively of the participants claimed that their economic status influences their use of illicit substances, while 49% and 48% respectively disagree, and 2% and 4% respectively claimed they are not sure.

The North Bank Region, Upper River Region, and West Coast Region indicate with 40%, 46%, and 41% respectively of the respondents asserting that their use of illicit substances is influenced by their economic status, whereas 53%, 53%, and 54% disagreed, and 7%, 2%, and 5% respectively are uncertain.

The findings show a divided opinion on the influence of economic status on substance abuse among the people engaged. In Central River Region, most of the people agreed that their use of substances is influenced by their economic status, whereas Greater Banjul and Lower River Region show a balanced opinion between agree and disagree. In North Bank, Upper River Region, and West Coast Region, most of the participants claim that their economic status does not influence their use of substances. This shows that many people are using illicit substances due to lack of meaningful engagement, while others are using it for pleasure.

5.3. Impact on individuals and families

Figure 13: Substance abuse effect on health

The graph above illustrates the perceived effect of substance abuse on health among the surveyed population. The results show that 47% of the respondents believe that substance abuse negatively impacted their health, while 52% disagree, and 1% are unsure. These findings suggest a strong awareness among the surveyed population about the potential health risks associated with substance abuse. Individuals who believe substance abuse negatively impacts their health reported a wide range of health problems, including respiratory issues (coughing, chest pain, shortness of breath), digestive problems (stomach pain, ulcers, nausea), mental health issues (anxiety, paranoia), physical weakness (fatigue, lethargy), weight loss, and other symptoms such as headaches, fever, insomnia, heart problems, and skin issues. These responses highlight the diverse range of health problems associated with substance abuse, emphasizing the detrimental effects on both physical and mental well-being.

Figure 14: Substance abuse effects on family relationships

The graph above illustrates the perceived impact of substance usage on participants' relationships with their family members. The most common negative consequence reported was an increase in conflicts, with 37% of the respondents reporting that their usage of illicit substances has raised the level of disputes between them and their family members, while 30% and 11% reported that their substance usage has caused emotional distancing and financial problems between them and their families, respectively. A significant majority of participants (51%) reported that their use of substances has no impact on the relationship between them and their family members. The findings highlight to some extent that quite a significant percentage of the participants believed that the use of illicit substances has yielded negative outcomes on their relationships with their family members, particularly a rise in conflicts and emotional distancing. On the contrary, many believed that their use of illicit substances had no impact on the relationship between them and their family members.

Figure 15: Regional Comparison

In the CRR, GBA, and LRR, 19%, 28%, and 27%, respectively, of the participants reported that their use of substances has caused emotional distancing between them and their family members, while 7%, 8%, and 11% respectively reported financial problems, and 29%, 27%, and 27% respectively reported an increase in conflict. Additionally, 44%, 36%, and 34%, respectively, reported that their use of substances has no impact on the relationship between them and their family members.

In NBR, URR, and WCR, the most common negative effects reported were a rise in conflicts, with 28%, 33%, and 28% respectively, while 20%, 21%, and 22% respectively reported emotional distancing, and 5%, 9%, and 11% respectively reported financial problems. Moreover, 46%, 36%, and 39%, respectively, reported that their use of substances has no impact on the relationship between them and their family members.

Findings reveal a unanimous agreement among participants across all regions in The Gambia. A large percentage of the participants agreed that their use of substances has no negative effects on their relationship with them and their family members; however, a very significant percentage of the participants believe that their use of illicit substances has detrimental effects on the relationship between them and their family members, particularly emotional distancing and raising conflicts.

5.4. Information on social environment

Table 8: Ratings on the number of individuals in their area who are users of illicit substances

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev	Min	Max
Youths' Usage Rate	1338	7.137	2.371	1	10

The table above shows the participants' ratings of the number of individuals in their area who are users of illicit substances if out of every ten individuals were to be selected at random in their area and are users of substances. It shows that, on average, out of every ten selected individuals in every area at random, 7.137 individuals are using illegal substances. This shows a high rate of illicit substance consumption among youths in The Gambia. stopped

Table 9: Perceived Substance Usage Rates Among Youths Categorized by Region

Region	Youths' Usage Rating
Central River Region	7.245
Greater Banjul Area	7.534
Lower River Region	6.365
North Bank Region	7.121
Upper River Region	7.104
West Coast Region	7.136

The table above represents participants' estimates of the number of individuals in their area who are likely to be illicit substance users out of every ten individuals selected randomly, categorized by regions. Greater Banjul Area has the highest average usage rate at 7.534, followed closely by Central River Region at 7.245. The Lower River Region stands out with the lowest average usage rate at 6.365, which is notably below the overall average (7.137). These regional averages suggest some variability in illicit consumption across the regions, with the Greater Banjul Area performing the best and the Lower River Region lagging. The overall mean of 7.137 reflects a relatively consistent pattern across most regions, except the Lower River Region.

Table 10: Perceived Substance Usage Rates Among Youths, Disaggregated by Education Level

Region	youths' usage rate
ECD	8.333
Informal	7.339
None	7.385
Primary	7.124
Senior Secondary	6.461
Tertiary	6.975
Upper Basic	6.611

Table 4 illustrates the participants' estimates of the number of individuals likely to be illicit substance users out of every ten individuals selected randomly, categorized by participants' educational level. It shows that respondents with ECD educational level reported the highest average perceived substance usage rate at 8.33, while those with Upper Basic education reported the lowest at 6.611. Respondents with individuals with neither formal nor informal (none), primary education, and informal education recorded relatively high average perceived usage rates of 7.385, 7.124, and 7.339, respectively. Meanwhile, individuals with Tertiary and secondary education reported moderate perceived usage rates of 6.461 and 6.975, respectively. The finding shows that participants with neither formal nor informal education have the highest perception of the usage rate, which is just by the standard deviation (2.58183).

5.5. Information on the availability and accessibility of rehabilitation services for substance abusers in the Gambia

Figure 16: Barriers to accessing rehabilitation services

The figure 16 above illustrates the primary barriers to accessing rehabilitation services in The Gambia. The most common barrier identified is the lack of information, with 42%. Most of the respondents cited that they have no idea about the existence of rehabilitation centers in The Gambia. Cost and distance to travel were also major challenges for many participants, with 37% and 26% of respondents, respectively. Discrimination and other factors were also cited by 21% and 12% of respondents, respectively. The data underscores the critical need to address information gaps and improve accessibility to rehabilitation services. The prevalence of cost and distance as barriers highlights the importance of affordability and geographic accessibility in ensuring equitable access to care. In addition, the presence of discrimination as a barrier emphasizes the need to address systemic issues and promote inclusivity within rehabilitation settings.

Figure 17: Barriers to accessing rehabilitation services by region:

The above figure 17 shows the obstacles participants believe are the primary challenges people face when trying to access rehabilitation services in The Gambia. In the Central River region, cost affordability and distance to travel, with 34% and 36%, respectively, are seen as the main obstacles to accessing rehabilitation services in The Gambia, while 12% claim it is stigma and discrimination.

In the Greater Banjul Area and West Coast Region, 39% and 37%, respectively, assert that the main challenge of accessing rehabilitation services is a lack of information, while 25% and 21% claim the primary challenge is cost affordability, and 16% and 18% believe it is stigma and discrimination.

North Bank Region, Lower River Region, and Central River Region, with 29%, 36%, and 25%, respectively, of the respondents, argue that the main barrier of accessing rehabilitation services is cost, while 23%, 34%, and 32%, respectively, believe it is the distance to travel, and 34%, 13%, and 22%, respectively, believe it is a lack of information. A significant percentage of 15%, 11%, and 11% of respondents in NBR, URR, and LRR, respectively, claim that the primary challenge of accessing rehabilitation services is stigma and discrimination.

5.6. Qualitative analysis

The reason why substance users engaged in the act is cross-cutting across regions, with most respondents giving the same set of issues, ranging from unemployment and peer influence to lack of parental guidance, as highlighted by an interviewee. Also, the issue of parental guidance is a major factor, as many of the substance users are believed to be not under strict parental guidance. Some respondents also highlighted losing parents at a young age and inadequate home training. For other respondents, the reasons for substance abuse might be the fact that some individuals are marginalized in society, with the belief that they cannot make any useful impact in this life, and this tends to affect their psyche. The increase in the deportation of youths from Europe is also a driver. One of the specific situations in which young people find themselves vulnerable to substance use is due to a lack of employment and being repatriated from Europe. The caregivers also influence; for example, if parents start sending their children to buy and sell substances at an early age, when they grow, they will end up trying it, they will want to taste it, and they may become one of substance abusers. Respondents also highlighted that poverty leads youth into drug abuse. Due to financial hardship, some young people cannot attend school or pursue further education. The low level of education caused by poverty can influence them to use substances, as they may not fully understand the consequences of drug use.

Here, we explored the pre- and post-behaviors and attitudes of substance users in society. Many of the respondents expressed that substance users are usually very calm, easy-going, and respectful individuals in society,

but once they start using substances, they become very aggressive and are accompanied by so much negativity. The most commonly used substances in the Gambia include marijuana, cannabis, and alcohol, as stated by the respondents, because they are cheap.

The level of awareness of substance users towards the substances has raised different views across communities. In some communities, they believe the users are very well aware of the dangers and consequences of their actions, while in others, they believe the users know the consequences, but they are searching for something deeper with the belief that they will only get it by taking substances. Some respondents believe the youths engaged in substance abuse do not know the dangers and consequences of their actions, and they believe introducing substance abuse education in our education curricula will go a long way in sensitizing and helping the youths understand the dangers of their activities. Peers, social media, and schools have a huge influence in helping prevent or reduce substance abuse in societies by helping to sensitize people about the effects of abusing substances. "The school is the best place where you can build good character for the children and educate them about drugs," a respondent said.

Respondents suggested several strategies they believe could effectively reduce substance use among youths in their communities or villages, emphasizing employment creation, awareness campaigns, skill development, and strong law enforcement. Respondents frequently mentioned the need for strengthening the border controls and being vigilant about foreigners entering the country with illicit substances. Furthermore, participants also emphasized awareness programs (radio talk show, TV program, community outreach, etc.) on educational initiatives targeting schools and communities. Moreover, participants also highlighted that family-based interventions are essential to help guide and engage youths on the impact of illicit substances.

In addition, stricter law enforcement measures were suggested, with a focus on pushing drug dealers and users. A participant noted that, "Drug enforcement agency should try and be very strict on drug users and dealers and impose heavy punishment on them." Another participant stated that "Drug enforcement agency should try and target large-scale dealers, as catching only users will not curb the problem."

Family and community-based interventions were highlighted as mechanisms that are important to address drug abuse among youths. A lot of the participants emphasized the central role of families in guiding and supporting their children. Participants vowed that parents are very casual in this stage; they need to sit with their children and talk to them about the hazards so they will be mindful of using drugs. Also, participants highlighted a very important point, which stated that "Role modeling in a family is very key; I can remember the time I was going to school; if people came to visit and wanted to smoke in front of the children, my dad would send them out of the house." If every family does the same, then smoking may be reduced. Participants also stressed the role of the broader community in playing its part. A participant from CRR-SOUTH suggested that "The community should start talking with the young people; for example, here in Bansang, the community tries to gather various youths and talk to them about drugs and things affecting them" (P2). This approach was also used in URR, where participants called for communities to support each other and motivate young people to strive for societal recognition.

Participants across all regions highlighted that drug abuse among youths significantly impacts their communities/villages. Increased crime rate (pickpockets, armed robbers, robbing people day and night) was mentioned by all regions as a direct consequence of creating an insecure environment. Also, education and productivity are affected, as noted that youths who should be contributing productively to the agricultural sector are not doing so, and many potential contributors to society become mentally ill or unable to do anything for themselves, ultimately disrupting the future workforce. In addition, the participants highlighted that it also affects the economic status of families; in a case when your child's health is not good because of drug usage, whatever you have, you will put on their health, reducing household incomes and savings, and increasing additional family stress.

The importance of parental monitoring and job creation was emphasized by the participants. According to participants, the government should create job opportunities, as the lack of employment is a root cause of both drug abuse and irregular migration. This emphasizes how crucial it is to solve financial difficulties to lessen the appeal of substance abuse. Furthermore, participants stressed the need for parental participation. They highlighted that family members should supervise their children from an early age to discourage negative habits. These recommendations emphasize how effective family guidance can be in preventing problems. In order to provide alternatives to substance use, the government can build a skill center that will engage the students, build more schools, and create employment, emphasizing the value of vocational training. Advocating that substance use should be included in the schools' curriculum, she proposed adding drug education to school curricula to increase awareness of the risks associated with substance misuse among youth.

Participants placed a strong emphasis on overcoming structural barriers to information distribution and running awareness campaigns. This emphasizes how increasing media access is necessary to improve awareness and sensitization campaigns. Respondents strongly advocated for stricter enforcement of existing laws, like the Tobacco Act, emphasizing that offenders should face severe penalties. They also called for better support for the Drug Law Enforcement Agency (DLEA), stating, "The government should provide adequate resources and fair salaries to help them carry out their duties without fear or bias. The participant further stressed the importance of targeting drug dealers, asserting that severe punishments for drug dealers would curb the availability of illicit substances. This approach highlights the significance of legal and regulatory frameworks in combating drug abuse.

5.7. Key information interview with DLEAG and ministry of health

Drug Law Enforcement Agency, The Gambia (DLEAG)

Awareness Campaigns and Gaps in Drug Control Policies

DLEAG established the Drug Matter Reduction Public Affairs Unit, later renamed the Media and Advocacy Unit. They have launched numerous campaigns to raise awareness about the dangers of substances, including weekly radio programs on various stations and TV broadcasts that run concurrently to educate the public about drug dangers. They also organize community and school outreach programs aimed at informing people about the risks of drug use. Additionally, there is a Drug-Free Club, formed by teachers' coordinators from different schools, to ensure the continuity of these clubs within schools for students. DLEAG is currently undergoing significant reforms, including updates to some of its policies and strategies. Meanwhile, the Ministry of Justice is developing new light penalties that are not covered in existing control policies. It was noted that while the government provides subsidies, they are not sufficient for DLEAG to fully implement its strategies and policies. Drug cases are becoming increasingly complex; new drugs frequently emerge in society, necessitating the development of strategies to counter them. Consequently, DLEAG states they need adequate resources, such as well-equipped laboratories with modern testing tools for suspected drugs, sophisticated detection equipment at borders, ports, and airports, as well as sufficient human resources, vehicles, and other necessary equipment motorcycles.

Effective Strategies in Controlling Drug Abuse:

According to DLEAG, strategies are implemented daily to make the agency more effective. One of these strategies is participation in community programs. Sometimes, groups of individuals, SOEs, and NGOs organize programs and invite the Drug Demand Reduction Unit to sensitize the community about drugs, which is a very effective way of sensitizing people about drugs and their effects.

DLEAG is also engaged in many drug demand reduction programs, like TV shows, community outreach, and radio station shows, to sensitize people about the side effects of drugs. Even in the Drug Control Act, Section 15 sub-sections 1m & G emphasized that people be well-sensitized and offered foster support. They believe that if people are better informed about the health and legal implications of drugs, the number of people who are going into drugs will be very minimal, or some will quit or reduce how they use it. The most effective way for the agency to minimize the prevalence and use of substances is through sensitization through school outreach, community outreach, and TV and radio shows.

As far as enforcing the agency's strategies is concerned, the agency faces many challenges, including mobility, resources, and human capacity. They also highlighted that in the process of carrying out their duty, they encountered armed individuals while their personnel were usually not armed, which usually hindered them from carrying out their duty effectively

Youth Statistics on Drug Abuse and Conviction and Release Rates:

The 2023 report shows that 466 youths between 18 to 35 years old were arrested for smuggling or using substances, and this represents 74% of the arrests made by the agency in 2023.

Social and Economic Impact of Drug Abuse:

Also, under the influence of drugs, a person may sexually violence another person. Substance abuse has also increased the rates of theft in society. Most of the abusers are not working, and as a result, they engage in theft to buy these substances. In society, every individual should play the role of a police officer to reduce the rate of abuse by reporting the users. Community policing should be well practiced in society.

Discriminations also play a significant role in the massive involvement of youths in drug abuse. Most of the time, when a person starts using substances, people start pointing fingers at him. which usually makes the person think that he is not fit here and this will make the individual go to the ghettos, where he will be embraced. These people should cooperate with us and make them feel they are part of us; as time goes on, they will realize what they are doing is not good. Some of these individuals are victims of circumstances; once they get into drugs, sometimes it is very difficult to get out of it, and in this, they need psychosocial support, counseling, and a therapist.

Rehabilitation and Post-Release Support

DLEAG does not have a rehabilitation center for convicted individuals. However, they said they already have a plot of land where the institution wants to build this rehabilitation center and we have some funds but the funds are not enough because we want it to be a standard one. In the Gambia, once you are convicted, you are either fined, imprisoned, or both. After they are discharged, there should be a follow-up or integration program, but resources are not there to do such.

Mistry of health (Public health)

Understanding substance abuse among youths

MoH reported that recently they received many cases at the health facilities that relate to drug abuse by young people, both boys and girls. Most of the frequent drug cases are related to Kush. Substance abuse is causing harm to society and economically, most of the victims spend lots of money to buy medication when the drug goes wrong in their system. The cases are not limited to just those using Kush or marijuana but alcohol as well. According to

participants, some youths take substances as a coping mechanism when they face social and economic stress, and that's affecting most of our youths.

Family instability or lack of parental oversight role in substance abuse among youths

Participants highlighted that family instability contributes a lot to drug abuse because traditional and cultural practices play a role in how children are brought up; parents are expected to give good home training to their children and not allow the child to move any random guy around that will influence them in this drug abuse. Parental guides are very key in shaping the lives of youths.

Significant changes or trends in substance abuse behaviors over the past few years

In the center (Banjulinding Health Center), the data collected on substance abuse cases has increased significantly as compared to the previous years. Every year they record and hear about new types of drugs without resistance, prevention, and control in the country.

The public health officers do a campaign and sensitization relating to the adverse impact of drugs on youth and societies, in which parents are also sensitized to keep their children away from the children or else it will have more health implications.

Specific cultural or societal practices in this community that could indirectly promote substance abuse among youths

When it comes to societal practices, there is a norm among youth to believe that if you are not using drugs, you are not seen as the fit guy or strong-headed guy. These are things that promote or influence youths into drugs. Another thing is societal stress. Believe in society. If you are stressed, drugs help you to relieve from the stress leading youth into drugs.

During the rampant cases of the Kush, we were working directly with the youths' key health education program for the youths in the community. You can see that participation among youths is always good, as the drug directly affects them and was discussed with the danger of this substance to their health. We also normally have health programs on the radio, and we use them to discuss the harmfulness of these substances with society.

The most common health problems you encounter among youths who abuse substances

According to the MoH, there are lots of health problems addicts encounter, such as drug-induced psychosis and the mania substances that affect the psychological thinking indifferent to people in the society, and again, it can develop neurotic problems. The neuro is responsible for all the coordination, so when conduction arises, it can cause commotion in the families when he/she assaults another family member, bringing conflict in society.

Some of the health issues faced can be short-term and long-term; the short-term are the ones such as the falling back of the tongue or swollen lips and tongue. The long-term effect is the affection of the mental health and causes mental imbalance.

Particular cases or incidents that highlight the severe health impacts of substance abuse among youths in your experience

There are many cases in which there is a need for intervention, e.g., where someone's tongue is swollen, if they do not intervene, the tongue will block the airway; in other instances, where the patient is hallucinated, he/she can kill himself/herself without realizing that he/she is killing himself/herself; during such instances, they do intervene to help the patient. If they abuse these drugs, if immediate actions are not taken, it can lead to death.

Prevention and public health efforts

According to the participants, there are programs under the Ministry of Health on the communication units to sensitize youths about the impact of drugs. They have enacted the Tobacco Act 2015, which prevents youths from smoking. Recently, police officers were on patrol to seize Caesar and other types of substances. The Ministry also reaches out to the community to sensitize the youths to the dangers of these drugs.

A task force was also created when there were frequent cases of Kush. Members of the task force were stakeholders from different sectors with the aim of controlling the rate of the usage of the drug.

There was a task force called MCD and health promotions; they also have done a lot in regards to addressing the issue of drugs in the country by sensitizing about drug abuse and again, community engagement with the youths organizing football matches and after the game they organize sessions with these youths discussing the effects of drug abuse.

According to the MoH, these efforts pay dividends because the number of cases is reduced after the interventions from the government, NGOs, and other stakeholders are implemented. The interventions are important and have yielded improvement.

Strategies implemented or observed that successfully reduce substance abuse among youths

MoH collaborates with DLEAG, schools, communities, and also the security border officers in sensitizing youths about the impact of drugs.

Additional measures should be implemented to reduce substance abuse among youths

Participants appeal to the government to strengthen the security at the main border post/entry points since the drugs are not manufactured here and most of the drugs we see around are smuggled by people. Also, the law should be fully enforced on all people regardless of status so that the rate of usage will be drastically reduced. The issue of fighting drug abuse should not be left only in one sector; it requires joining hands. Other sectors should take responsibility and try to contribute to stopping the entry of these drugs; we cannot control the abuse of substances while the entry points are not strengthened.

3. CHALLENGES AND RECOMMENDATIONS FROM THE PARTICIPANTS OF THE KII (DLEAG and MoH)

- According to the participants, most of the challenge is the attitude change. When you give them health education and inform some of the youths about the harmful effects of the substances, it is always difficult to see changes in their attitude towards the substance. The society also influenced many youths into taking the substance because of peer influences.
- There should be collaboration between stakeholders to stop drug abuse; some of the sectors will be doing great work while the other sectors are weak to play their part; things will not work, and sectors are expected to effectively play their roles or else things will not work. For example, if the health workers are trying to reach out to communities to sensitize the youths while community leaders are not playing their role at the community level to address this, it will be very difficult to see changes among youths, showing that the collaboration principle and the enforcement are weak and there are still lapses in educating and sensitizing youths in communities.
- The other challenge is the availability of resources. When we receive a case that needs urgent attention for all to converge to help, the obstacle is always a resource problem to help that individual, so what they do normally is to take them to a referring hospital at Kanifing or Edward Francis Small Teaching Hospital at

Banjul in most cases. The lack of these materials to take care of these needs is a problem and a challenge in these health centers.

- Allocation of adequate resources. Substance abuse is getting more complex by the day; as a result, we need adequate allocation of resources, including an increase in budget allocation to the agency, vehicles, motorbikes, sophisticated detective materials that can easily detect drugs, and other gadgets that will make our work easy
- DLEAG should also be giving scholarships both at home and abroad to capacitate its personnel because there is a global approach to fighting drugs. The more people are trained, the more skilled they will acquire and the more knowledge they will apply in the fight against drugs.
- DLEAG should have effective school outreach, like launching Drug-Free Clubs in schools and building their capacities on drug-related issues. They are going to learn that early-age drugs and their related substances are not goods
- There should be effective community sensitization; we believe people are going to do community policing effectively by reporting those who are dealing drugs or arresting them and taking them to the right authorities.
- There should also be effective ads for drugs on radios, TVs, and signboards. There should be flyers at the country's entry points, like at the Airport and the Borders. This will make people know when entering the country that these drugs are prohibited.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

4.1. Discussion

This study aimed to assess the socio-economic factors that influence substance abuse among youths in The Gambia. A mixed-method approach combined quantitative and qualitative data collection and analysis methods. The study covered all regions of The Gambia using a snowball sampling method for the exercise. The positive trend of unemployment has imposed significant challenges on many young individuals, and one of its concerning negative consequences is the rise in substance use. As confessed by many, "they usually sit in ghettos due to lack of engagement, frustration, and lack of purpose." These claims are substantially supported by the findings. The findings show that a large portion of the respondents (47%) believe that their use of illicit substances is influenced by their socioeconomic status. However, a notable portion (50%) believe it does, and 3% reported having no idea about the connection. The majority of the respondents (64%) associated low-income status families with a higher likelihood of substance abuse among youths, while a notable portion disagreed (32%), and 4% were unsure.

Peer pressure, which has become a big concern to many, particularly parents, is substantially supported by the findings. In an effort to avoid being labeled different or gain acceptance, many young individuals have often given in to the habit of their friends. It becomes easier for one to try illicit substances when surrounded by individuals who use illicit substances. Of the respondents, 61% reported that their initial use of illicit substances is a result of peer pressure, while 39% believed that peer pressure has no influence on their initial use of illicit substances. The findings were confirmed by other researchers like Bah's (2018) study in the Gambia, where he investigated the risk and prevalence of drug misuse among street children in Gambia, with a focus on those in car parks. The findings revealed that the Street children, like other children, use drugs primarily because of peer pressure, with the main purpose of getting high to relieve stress, gain group recognition, and be trusted by peers. It's also aligned with Nega and Chacko, (2021) done in NEKEMTE in Ethiopia, focusing on 12 street children and a few employees. Their findings showed that peers perform a leading and protective function, as well as give and encourage influence and leadership responsibilities.

It's a common cultural practice in Africa in general and Gambia in particular that children are usually sent on errands by elders, which is rooted in obedience and values of respect. Children are expected to assist their elders in certain tasks including buying items from markets or shops, where the items can be drugs or items related, which exposes many children to harmful substances or illicit substances at a very early age. Of the respondents, 71% reported that they were exposed to substances at a young age either by their family members or relatives causing most of them to adopt the habit of substance use.

Schools, as an esteemed ground for education and discipline, have become destruction sites for many young individuals. Due to the easy access to illicit substances, many young individuals start experimenting with drugs during school hours, which usually disrupts the learning environment and undermines academic performance. The result shows that 49% of the respondents started using substances while they were going to school and 51% admit that they started using substances after they left school.

Rehabilitation centers are very crucial in every society due to the rapid increase in substance abuse in the communities, but due to their availability and accessibility, it has become a big concern to many.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS AND POLICYMAKERS

- i. To reduce the influence of economic status on substance usage among youths in The Gambia, support programs like financial literacy workshops and youth development projects and initiatives that create opportunities for youths, and vocational training should be implemented. This will mitigate the hardship of unemployment, reduce the loitering of many youths by engaging them in something, and help them know how to utilize the little resources they have. As confessed by many youths, they usually sit in ghettos and use substances due to their lack of employment.
- ii. Youth-centered and community-based interventions that emphasize providing recreational activities, mentorship programs, and education on the dangers of substance abuse should be prioritized to help reduce the negative impact of substance abuse by empowering youths with resources, knowledge, and positive social networks.
- iii. Many of the substance users usually share substances with peers; this shows the relatively low perceptions of the negative consequences of sharing substances among youths. Public health campaigns and programs should be created that will help youths to know the consequences of sharing substances, like the possibility of contracting diseases, by educating them via dramas and videos.
- iv. Family and community engagement should be prioritized to educate families on the effects of substance abuse, peer influence, and peer pressure, as well as how to open non-judgmental conversations with their children. This could improve the relationship between most parents and their children
- v. Peer influence has a significant negative impact on youths nowadays. As a result, early education about its potential effects, targeting middle and high schools with anti-drug campaigns and lessons about peer influence and peer pressure, such as group discussions in school, could help them to become more aware of how peer pressure operates and even give them the tools to handle them. This will also help children to differentiate between toxic and beneficial friends, build resistance to peer pressure, and develop confidence to resist negative influences from friends.
- vi. Drug Law Enforcement Agency The Gambia (DLEAG) should impose severe punishment, collaborate with the communities, disrupt supply networks, and strictly observe mitigation policies to reduce the prevalence of illicit substances in the country, particularly in the borders. DLEAG should also collaborate with health providers to guide minor offenders toward treatment rather than punishing them.
- vii. The data indicates that the majority of substance users reported early exposure to illicit substances, which subsequently led to their substance use. To address this, strict laws should be enacted to prohibit individuals

under the age of 18 from being sent to purchase illegal substances. Implementing such measures could help minimize early exposure to illicit substances and, in turn, mitigate substance abuse.

- viii. Stricter regulations should be enforced on the sale, consumption, and distribution of substances. Law enforcement efforts should be strengthened to combat drug trafficking and distribution. Also, international cooperation is essential to address transnational drug trafficking and illicit drug production.
- ix. The government should introduce more initiatives that foster youth dialogue, such as forums and community events where young people can discuss the challenges they face in society and collaboratively find positive solutions. This recommendation stems from findings suggesting that peer pressure can have a significant role in steering youths away from substance use when addressed constructively.
- x. The government should collaborate with Drug Law Enforcement Agency, The Gambia (DLEAG) to prioritize the rehabilitation of addicted youths by establishing or enhancing rehabilitation centers. Allowing addicted youths to remain untreated in society poses a significant risk by normalizing substance abuse and influencing more youths to engage in it. Addressing the root causes, such as peer pressure, through targeted interventions is essential.
- xi. Increase public health resources, leverage technology, and decentralize services: expand and better equip public facilities in all regions as they are the most utilized for substance abuse treatment. Use telemedicine to provide remote counseling and support services to youths in areas where physical rehabilitation facilities are not easily accessible.
- xii. Training for Staff: Provide specialized training to improve the expertise and compassion of rehabilitation center staff.

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